

OPTIMIZATION OF A REVERSE LOGISTICS NETWORK FOR ENERGY RECOVERY UNDER ENVIRONMENTAL CONSTRAINTS

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ABSTRACT: *Implementing sustainable logistics today represents a performance challenge and a competitive advantage for most companies. One of the current global challenges that concerns many scientists is the massive rate of waste that is increasing day by day. In this mixed context of environmental regulations and customer requirements, researchers and scientists are trying to find innovative approaches to meet this challenge with a greater emphasis on waste management and recycling. The circular economy, on the other hand, aims to reduce waste as much as possible and promote sustainable use of natural resources, through smarter design of products, longer use, recycling, as well as regenerating nature. Given the trends in global economic development, this widespread concern represents a valuable opportunity to contribute to the sustainability of supply chains through the optimal use of existing resources, or even a replacement of these resources with renewable consumption which leads to reducing environmental pollution. (reduce CO2 emissions), and adapt to economic constraints (minimization of costs). In the industrial sector, end-of-life product management is one of the effective solutions that allows manufacturers to ensure recovery and treatment used products. The objective of this work is to propose a logistics chain reverse dedicated to the collection, sorting and treatment of household waste in the city of Tlemcen, this minimizes both transport costs and waste volumes, and reduces CO2 emissions by providing a source for domestic consumption.*

KEYWORDS: *Reverse logistics; location; Circular economy; waste management; waste recovery*

1 INTRODUCTION

Reverse logistics is considered one of the most promising solutions for capturing the remaining value of used products. Waste management and energy systems are often linked, either directly through waste-to-energy technologies or indirectly through resource recovery processes (such as materials, oils, manure or sludge) that use energy in their processes for which recycling processes provide raw materials. In order to guarantee the proper purpose of waste which can take several forms in particular, solid waste such as wood, steel, or organic waste or even spent fuel waste, where each type undergoes certain specific transformation processes such as incineration for the elimination of infectious waste such as dressings, disposable syringes, etc. or a recycling process for the recovery of raw materials as well as methanization processes, organic composting, etc. These processes aim to contribute to material or energy recovery by

reducing CO2 emissions, reducing the volume of waste, giving a second life to electronic waste (Remanufacturing) and avoiding nighttime dumps. Transportation cost represents approximately 40 to 50 percent of total logistic costs Chikhalkar and al. (2014), it generates from the collection point to the treatment site 20 percent of greenhouse gas emissions CERES and al. (2016), to confront these loads and ensure proper functioning of the reverse networks, careful analyzes must be carried out in order to determine the best locations for collection and sorting centers followed by optimal allocation of different customers to the collection center, while minimizing transport costs and CO2 emissions from vehicles. The goal is to develop a mathematical model to minimize the costs of different activities in the supply chain, from customers to processing centers, including collection and sorting centers. We will deduce solutions to energy consumption and greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions. This study is

supported by the economic will of the country according to the forecasts of the Minister of the Environment and Renewable Energy who is more concerned about the volume of waste which according to statistics will reach 74 million tonnes in 2030. Thus the ambition of the Ministry of the Environment and Renewable Energy (MEER) would be to adopt a new waste management model by moving from the traditional waste management method towards a circular economy, the aim of which is to achieve average 30 to 40 percent of waste. In this regard, about the circular economy, green legislation and green manufacturing are increasing. This contribution aims to highlight the contribution of the circular economy to understanding waste management in the new circular logic, and this through the Algerian case, where waste management remains traditional and centered on the implementation landfill and burial. The objective is to develop a facility allocation model in order to plan and manage a household waste treatment system taking into consideration the environmental impact and geographical circumstances. The choice of this issue corresponds perfectly to the current global challenge, which aims to limit the waste of natural resources, reduce environmental impacts and increase the efficiency of the exploitation of natural resources at all stages of the product by focusing on carbon emissions. CO₂.

2 LITERATURE REVIEW

In the recent years, growing concerns over ecological sustainability have compelled academicians and industry practitioners to integrate activities such as recycling, repair, remanufacturing, reuse and refurbishing into their network design for the purpose of maximum value-added recovery Lechner and Reimann, (2020); Koshta and al. (2021). Such activities seek to recover valuable resources from used products through the systematic and integrated approach of RL Chukwuebuka and al. (2021). Reverse logistics (RL) is considered an essential part of the concept of the circular economy, a regenerative approach to the industrial economy Bernon and al. (2018) Swanson and al. (2018) and is one of the fastest growing waste management research Sehnem and al. (2019). Unlike traditional linear logistics which start from the producer to the end customer, reverse logistics entails the reverse flow that determines a closed-loop supply chain in combination with linear logistics. In fact, a process in which a producer systematically takes in previously transported goods from the consumers for subsequent remanufacturing; reuse, recycling, or disposal is

what defines reverse logistics Cricelli and al. (2019). Puzio, E. (2018) presented the theoretical foundations related to the concept of reverse logistics, defines the directions of waste flow in the waste management system and discusses the waste disposal chain. In the literature, several works have discussed the problem of waste management by considering several parameters. These include the work Salimi and al.(2016) or the basic model considered in this study, aimed to design reverse logistics as part of the supply chain in order to minimize the total cost of recycling municipal solid waste. The problem of municipal waste emissions using reverse logistics management is addressed by Wang, J. (2016). A new approach to reverse logistics network design and planning is suggested and formulated by Yu and al. (2016). Another multi-echelon reverse logistics model is developed by Liao and al. (2018). It maximizes total profit by handling products returned for repair, remanufacturing, recycling, reuse, or incineration/landfill. The authors have proposed a model for locating reverse logistics facilities that takes into account the reasonable location of logistics nodes. Chang and al. (2021). Xu and Yan .(2022) presented new municipal hazardous waste management methods and the internet of things.(Abdissa and al.(2022) used a descriptive research design to investigate the role of reverse logistics in used plastic bottle recycling and waste management in Ethiopia. (Ardi and al. (2023) proposed a robust optimization model for plastic waste management within the reverse logistics system in Jakarta. Peña-Montoya and al.(2020) proposed an adapted maturity model to measure maturity levels of reverse logistics aspects at small- and medium-sized enterprises in regions from Colombia in order to contribute to sustainable solid waste. Stallkamp and al. (2022) developed multiple exemplary multi-criteria optimization models to design an optimal recycling network. The models are deployed in a case study for plastic packaging waste in Europe for an advanced mechanical recycling process. While most research in the literature has focused on economic measures of LR, only a few studies have explored the ecological aspect in depth. Some of these recent studies are cited here. Demirel and al. (2016) designed a single product RL network for recycling end-of-life vehicles in Turkey. The mixed integer linear programming mathematical model developed in the study optimizes costs related to parts recovery, material recovery, and transportation, while it minimizes environmental degradation through reduced landfill quantities. Bal and Satoglu. (2018) developed a multi-facility and multi-product RL

network model for the recovery of household products from an emerging economy perspective. The authors stated that to be ecologically more responsible, manufacturers should not exceed their determined emissions level and should, instead, switch to eco-efficient transportation. Tosarkani and al. (2020) presented a sustainable reverse logistics network design for an electronic remanufacturer to enhance the green performance of recovery and remanufacturing plants along with maximizing profits. In another study published by Moslehi and al. (2021), a multi-objective optimization model for RL network design focusing on waste electronic and electrical products recycling through multiple levels was developed. The results of the study demonstrated that the recycling process gives an advantage to achieve environmental sustainability through strategically configured RL networks. The study of Kannan and al. (2021) proposed a multi-objective model for configuring a RL network design; it incorporates multiple products, multiple recovery facilities, multiple processing technologies, and a selection of vehicle types. The novelty of this study lies in its consideration of four green technologies (inspection, dismantling, repair/refurbishing, and recycling facilities), and its efforts to maximize return yield potential in the form of product, components, and material recovery. In the context of carbon neutrality, plastic ban, and green development, Chen and al. (2023) aimed to maximize the comprehensive interest of manufacturers in building a sustainable logistic network. They proposed a reverse logistics network model of a dual-channel model with multiple objectives. Safdar and al. (2020) authors in this paper aim to develop a multi-objective reverse logistics network model for e-waste management, the objectives of the model formulated are to maximize profit and minimize carbon emissions as well as maximize employment opportunities in a reverse logistics network. A three-tier recycling network model consisting of recycling centres,

testing and processing centres, reprocessing centres, power plants and landfill plants has been developed based on the special characteristics of medical waste. Qi and al. (2023). In summary, the majority of research literature begins from benefit recovery and takes the maximum or minimum cost as the objective function. However, economic benefit is only one of the benefits of reverse logistics, and environmental benefits cannot be ignored. Thus, it is necessary to take energy consumption or other indicators that can reflect the utilization of resources into consideration and to consider the balance between each indicator and the profit of each objective. In addition, how to efficiently achieve optimal design under multiple factors and objective functions has become a significant research topic and can be regarded as a typical optimization problem Chang and al. (2021). This paper formulates a dual-objective function optimization model that combines the delivery of the first network with the collection of the second network, minimizing the use of transport means, which is expressed in the minimization of transport costs accompanying energy consumption and CO2 emissions, while ensuring the satisfaction of customers, demanders and harvesters. An analysis and discussion are carried out to check the robustness of the results.

3 PROBLEM STATEMENT

The problem studied in this work deals with the collection and recovery of organic waste from customers to treatment and recovery centers. The network begins by providing a decision-making system on the choice of the location of the collection points on n candidate site then their assignments to the treatment centers taking into consideration the capacity of the collection points, the capacity of the trucks which provide transport as well as the distances and paths to the processing centers to be respected. The waste transported to the treatment centers can be as shown in the figure 1.

Fig1. Collection and recovery of organic waste

Following this collection, the waste is sent to various processing centers. Where 36% of the household waste collected is sent to an incinerator; 24% of the quantity collected is transferred to waste storage facilities, more commonly known as landfills. For cardboard, paper, plastics, electrical appliances, etc., an estimated 23% have a final destination within the recycling chain, and finally, for bio-waste, which is around 17%, it is sent to a composting center or a methanization unit. For each process requires techniques and processes which are described below.

3.1 Incineration

Incineration is one of the most important activities in an integrated waste management system due to its capacity to destroy hazardous waste, reduce the mass and volume of residues, and recover energy content from unrecyclable as well as recyclable materials having significant heat values Morselli and al. (2007). This technique is chosen by many intermunicipal unions because it occupies less space than the landfill and allows the recovery of waste, producing heat for useful purposes such as the distribution of hot water supplying the district heating network or the production of electricity Zhao and al. (2023). On the other hand, incineration has the disadvantage of producing toxic ash and polluted air during the incineration process. In the Kyoto Protocol, the incineration process is regarded as one of the major sources of greenhouse gases. In addition, the disposal of the ash residues is another problem that has to be dealt with, because they may contain toxic chemicals such as dioxins which can be hazardous to the environment and human health. Modern cleaning and emission control technologies such as gas purification can be adopted to lower their hazardous impact significantly Chen and al. (2012).

3.2 Landfill

Landfilling is defined as the disposal, compression and embankment fill of waste at appropriate sites Landfill for the moment is easy, adjustable with lower cost than the rest of disposal methods and stands alone as the only all waste material disposal method Vaverková. (2019). Although the disposal of waste in landfills has decreased, landfills are likely to remain an important part of integrated solid management systems all over the world. Comparative studies of various waste management (WM) methods (landfilling, incineration, composting etc.) show that among the treatment and disposal technological options, sanitary landfilling or open dumping is popular in most countries because of the relative

low cost and low-technical requirement Gonzalez and al. (2016); Feng and al. (2018). However, illegal and uncontrolled “landfills” (mostly known as open dumpsites) are, unfortunately, prevalent in many developing countries. Due to the widespread use of landfilling, even as of today, it is imperative to examine any environmental- and/or health-related issues that have emerged Siddiqua and al. (2022). Open dumpsites have been replaced by controlled landfills, also called technical landfill centers. The selection of sites for technical landfill centers is an important and necessary issue for the sanitary disposal of waste. Fateh and al. (2022). Technical landfill centers are different from open dumps because the waste is compacted in a hole and covered with a thin layer of soil every day.

3.3 Recycling

Recycling is a form of waste management that involves converting waste and other used materials into reusable products hence, improving the economy. These practices significantly reduce the quantity of waste disposed-off at the landfills hence, extending the life span of the landfill, reducing the amount of poisonous emissions from those facilities and saving a reasonable amount of fund for the authority Ugwu and al. (2021). Recycling comprises a set of processes that can be further classified according to different aspects. On the one hand the degree of processing, that takes place, leads to the following categories (Goorhuis and Bartl, 2011). The first category concerns product recycling in which the chemical and physical constitution of a product is maintained, but the product is not used for the original purpose (e.g. using tyres or glass bottles as building material). The second category is the recycling of materials in which the physical, but not the chemical constitution is destroyed (e.g. melting and reprocessing of metals, or recycling of fertilizers from food waste to the farming land). Recycling operations comprises a huge number of processes which can be more or less efficient. For recycling operations there is no comparable analogue formula as it exists for recovery. It is even unclear which measures could be taken to describe the efficiency of recycling. Equally the following instruments might be used to define the efficiency of recycling Bartl, A. (2014).

3.4 Methanization

Methanization also called anaerobic digestion is a biotechnological process through which a mixed microbial culture is broken down in the absence of oxygen, this fermentation is called digestate. As the organic matter (proteins, carbohydrates, fats)

degrades, it is converted to intermediates (hydrogen, volatile fatty acids, alcohols, etc.) and finally to biogas. Biogas is produced during anaerobic digestion (AD) of organic materials, carried out by a complex microbial community through multiple complicated biochemical reactions Rajaeifar and al. (2017). Biogas should be upgraded to biomethane prior to injection into the gas grid or use as a vehicle fuel Sahota and al. (2018). Given the unique advantageous of this renewable energy carrier, there has been a renewed interest globally in AD of various organic wastes including food wastes for biogas production Barati and al. (2017). Biogas can be used locally for heating or for combined heat and power production Liebetrau and al. (2020). Alternatively, energy producers can upgrade biogas to biomethane Ardolino and al. (2021). This upgrading includes removal of impurities and carbon dioxide from the gas. The greatest effort lies in removing the carbon dioxide due to its high concentration Zhou and al. (2017). The most commonly applied technologies for gas cleaning are membrane separation Scholes and al. (2012), water or chemical scrubbers, and pressure swing absorption (PSA). Once the CO₂ is removed, the final product is called biomethane which has similar properties to natural gas, allowing it to be directly substituted for natural gas and using the existing infrastructure and utilization technologies. Biomethane can be injected into gas grids or directly passed on to customers (e.g., local fuel stations); it also increases the share of green gas distributed to customers. Depending on local regulations, biomethane might need the addition of propane to adapt its calorific value and odorification when it is injected into the grid Abderezzak and al. (2012).

3.5 Composting

Unlike methanization, composting is a natural process of degradation or decomposition of organic matter by microorganisms under aerobic conditions. Sometimes, for the process to be successful, it must be performed under very optimum and controlled environment with the appropriate moisture level, aeration and temperature Atalia and al. (2015). The composting process must be managed properly by controlling the biological and oxygen demand as process passes through different stages till the final compost is achieved Haight, T. (2000).. In this organic waste composting process, the materials are decomposed into stabilized products useful as conditioners or fertilizers to the soil Pathak and al. (2011). The decomposing organisms are widespread in nature. They include actinomycetes, fungi and bacteria. These organisms are spread in many places

like in the soil, fruits, vegetables, dust, etc. According to Pathak and al. Pathak and al. (2011), composting is of two fundamental types, viz; aerobic and anaerobic. Aerobic composting takes place in the presence oxygen. This process produces some gaseous compounds like CO₂, and NH₃ in addition to water and heat Pathak and al. (2011). Anaerobic composting involves the decomposition of wastes without the presence of oxygen. This process gives out gaseous products like carbon dioxide (CO₂), methane (CH₄), ammonia (NH₃) and other gases in trace amounts with organic acids. This technique has being employed traditionally to compost mostly manure from animals and human sewage sludge. However, it has recently become common in green waste and MSW composting Guanzon and al. (2015). As beneficial as composting is, it takes a longer time to be ready, produces offensive odor, has long mineralization time, may contain some pathogens that can withstand high temperature to some extent, i.e., thermotolerant pathogens and insufficient nutrient content. All these have discouraged farmers from incorporating them as a means of sustainable agriculture. This made the synthetic counterpart (chemical fertilizers), which is readily available, preferred to the organic source, i.e., composting. Compost should be appreciated after the comparison of the advantages and disadvantages of the two sources of nutrients Ayilara and al. (2015).

The problem study ,can be formulated as an allocation location problem, which will be followed by a technical and economic study transport Benfriha and al (2022), Triqui and al (2016), which remains a very complex problem. In this context numerous decisions must be made by integrating constraints of varied nature depending on the characteristics of the product, the quantities involved, their destination, what means of transport used in terms of capacity and number, what environmental impact, etc. Waste processing can also be the source of greenhouse gas emissions into the atmosphere. Finally, to assess the carbon footprint of our waste, we must also take into account the CO₂ emissions generated during the manufacturing of the products or packaging that we then threw away.

4 MATHEMATICAL MODELING

The modeling is based on linear mixed integer programming with binary decision variables which represent opening or closing decisions, as well as integer decision variables representing the volumes of product classes to be distributed from upstream to downstream. In the proposed model the authors tried to be closer to reality by integrating: the

capacities of the centers, the volume of product transferred and the environmental footprint. The study of the problem was established in the context of a dynamic approach associated with a planning time horizon. The mathematical presentation of the model comes from the extension of the problem of locating plants with fixed charges under capacity constraints CFCFL (Capacitated Fixed Charge Facility Location) Guazzelli and al. (2018), while having the objective of minimizing costs relating to improvement perspectives of reverse logistics. Many fixed and variable costs are considered at the investment level of location, collection, processing for better management of physical flows between the different entities designing the reverse chain are presented below:

• **Sets**

$i \in I$	set of waste collection points.
$j \in J$	set of universities
$k \in K$	set of collecting and sorting center
$l \in L$	set of treatments units
$m \in M$	set of vehicles for transporting waste from waste collection points i to the collection center k
$n \in N$	set of vehicles for transporting waste from universities j to treatments units l .
$p \in P$	set of vehicles for transporting products from collection center k to treatments units l .

• **Data**

Fcl_k	Operating costs of the collecting center k
$CV1_m$	The fixed cost of using a vehicle m
$CV2_n$	The fixed cost of using a vehicle n
$CV3_p$	The fixed cost of using a vehicle p
a	The transport cost
h	Vehicle consumption rate
r	Vehicle CO2 emission factor
Cmx_k	Maximum collecting center capacity k
Cmn_k	Minimum collecting center capacity k
Qd_i	Maximum quantity of waste at collection points i .
Qu_j	Maximum quantity of waste at university j .
$Dist1_{i,k}$	Distance from collection points i to collecting center k
$Dist2_{j,l}$	Distance from universities j to treatment unit l .

$Dist3_{k,l}$	Distance from collecting centre k to treatment unit l
Dem_l	Demands of the treatment units
A	A large number
Variables de décisions	
X_k	$= \begin{cases} 1 & \text{choice of collecting center } k \\ 0 & \text{else} \end{cases}$
$W_{i,k,m}$	$= \begin{cases} 1 & \text{vehicle } m \text{ is used from collection point } i \text{ to collecting center } k \\ 0 & \text{else} \end{cases}$
$Z_{j,l,n}$	$= \begin{cases} 1 & \text{vehicle } n \text{ is used from university } j \text{ to treatment unit } l \\ 0 & \text{else} \end{cases}$
$B_{k,l,p}$	$= \begin{cases} 1 & \text{vehicle } p \text{ is used from collecting center } k \text{ to treatment unit } l \\ 0 & \text{else} \end{cases}$
$Vol1_{i,k,m}$	Volumes of waste delivered from the collection point i to the collecting center k using vehicle m .
$Vol2_{j,l,n}$	Volumes of waste delivered from the universities j to the 4 th treatment unit (composting, $l=4$) using vehicle n .
Qdc_k	The maximum quantity of waste collected in the center k
$Q1_{k,l,p}$	The quantity of the first type waste delivered from collecting center k to first treatment unit (landfill $l=1$) using vehicle p .
$Q2_{k,l,p}$	The quantity of the second type waste delivered from collecting center k to the second treatment unit (incineration $l=2$) using vehicle p .
$Q3_{k,l,p}$	The quantity of the third type waste delivered from collecting center k to the third treatment unit (recycling $l=3$) using vehicle p .
$Q4_{k,l,p}$	The quantity of the fourth type waste delivered from collecting center k to the fourth treatment unit (composting $l=4$) using vehicle p .
QL_l	The delivered quantity of the 1 st product at the first treatment unit (Landfill, $l=1$).
QLV_l	The sold quantity of the 1 st product at the first treatment unit (Landfill, $l=1$).
QLS_l	The stored quantity of the 1 st product at the first treatment unit (Landfill, $l=1$).
QI_l	The delivered quantity of 2 nd product at the first treatment unit (Waste incineration, $l=2$).
QIV_l	The sold quantity of the 2 nd product at the first treatment unit (Waste incineration, $l=2$).
QIS_l	The stored quantity of the 2 nd product at the first treatment unit (Waste incineration, $l=2$).
QR_l	The delivered quantity of the 3 rd product at the first treatment unit (Recycling, $l=3$).

QRV₁	The sold quantity of the 3 rd product at the first treatment unit (Recycling, l=3).
QRS₁	The stored quantity of the 3 rd product at the first treatment unit (Recycling, l=3).
QC₁	The delivered quantity of the 4 th product at the first treatment unit (Composting, l=4).
QCV₁	The sold quantity of the 4 th product at the first treatment unit (Composting, l=4).
QCS₁	The stored quantity of the 4 th product at the first treatment unit (Composting, l=4).
ECV	The quantity of CO2 emitted by the used vehicles in the studied network.
ECI	The quantity of CO2 emitted by the waste incineration at the 2 nd treatment unit

• **Objective function**

The objective of this study is to minimize the overall cost of the studied network, which includes : the operating cost of the collection center k, the cost of transporting the delivered quantity from collection point i to collection center k, the cost of vehicle utilization from collection point i to collection center k, the cost of transporting waste from universities j to treatment units l, including vehicle utilization costs, the cost of transporting different types of quantities to the treatment units l, and the cost of vehicle utilization from the collection center k to the treatment units l.

$$\begin{aligned}
 Min F = & \sum_k Fcl_k * X_k + \sum_i \sum_k \sum_m \alpha * Dist1_{i k} * Vol1_{i k m} + \sum_i \sum_k \sum_m CFV1_{i k m} * W_{i k m} + \\
 & \sum_j \sum_l \sum_n \alpha * Dist2_{j l} * Vol2_{j l n} + \sum_j \sum_l \sum_n CFV2_{j l n} * Z_{j l n} + \\
 & \sum_k \sum_l \sum_p \alpha * Dist3_{k l} * (Q1_{k 1 p} + Q2_{k 2 p} + Q3_{k 3 p} + Q4_{k 4 p}) + \sum_k \sum_l \sum_p CFV3_{K l p} * B_{k l p}
 \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

• **Under the constraints**

$$Qd_i = \sum_k \sum_m Vol1_{i k m} \quad \forall i \tag{2}$$

$$Vol1_{i k m} \leq A * W_{i k m} \quad \forall i \quad \forall k \quad \forall m \tag{3}$$

$$\sum_m W_{i k m} \leq 1 \quad \forall i \quad \forall k \tag{4}$$

$$\sum_i \sum_m Vol1_{i k m} \leq Cmx_k * X_k \quad \forall k \tag{5}$$

$$\sum_i \sum_m Vol1_{i k m} \geq Cmn_k * X_k \quad \forall k \tag{6}$$

$$\sum_i \sum_m Vol1_{i k m} = Qdc_k \quad \forall k \tag{7}$$

$$\sum_{l=1} \sum_p Q1_{k 1 p} = 0.24 * Qdc_k \quad \forall k \tag{8}$$

$$\sum_{l=2} \sum_p Q2_{k 2 p} = 0.36 * Qdc_k \quad \forall k \tag{9}$$

$$\sum_{l=3} \sum_p Q3_{k 3 p} = 0.23 * Qdc_k \quad \forall k \tag{10}$$

$$\sum_{l=4} \sum_p Q4_{k 4 p} = 0.17 * Qdc_k \quad \forall k \tag{11}$$

$$Qu_j = \sum_n Vol2_{j l n} \quad \forall j \quad \forall l: l=4 \tag{12}$$

$$VOL2_{j l n} \leq A * Z_{j l n} \quad \forall j \quad \forall l \quad \forall n \tag{13}$$

$$\sum_n Z_{j l n} \leq 1 \quad \forall j \quad \forall l \tag{14}$$

$$QL_1 = \sum_k \sum_p Q1_{k 1 p} \quad \forall l=1 \tag{15}$$

$$Q1_{k 1 p} \leq A * B_{k l p} \quad \forall k \quad \forall l=1 \quad \forall p \tag{16}$$

$$QI_2 = \sum_k \sum_p Q2_{k 2 p} \quad \forall l=2 \tag{17}$$

$$Q2_{k 2 p} \leq A * B_{k l p} \quad \forall k \quad \forall l=2 \quad \forall p \tag{18}$$

$$QR_3 = \sum_k \sum_p Q3_{k 3 p} \quad \forall l=3 \tag{19}$$

$$Q3_{k 3 p} \leq A * B_{k l p} \quad \forall k \quad \forall l=3 \quad \forall p \tag{20}$$

$$QC_4 = \sum_k \sum_p Q4_{k 4 p} + \sum_j \sum_n Vol2_{j l n} \quad \forall l=4 \tag{21}$$

$$Q4_{k 4 p} \leq A * B_{k l p} \quad \forall k \quad \forall l=4 \quad \forall p \tag{22}$$

$$\sum_p B_{k l p} \leq 1 \quad \forall k \quad \forall l \tag{23}$$

$$QL_1 = QLV_1 + QLS_1 \quad \forall l=1 \tag{24}$$

$$QI_2 = QIV_2 + QIS_2 \quad \forall l = 2 \quad (25)$$

$$QR_3 = QRV_3 + QRS_3 \quad \forall l = 3 \quad (26)$$

$$QC_4 = QCV_4 + QCS_4 \quad \forall l = 4 \quad (27)$$

$$QLV_1 = Dem_1 \quad \forall l = 1 \quad (28)$$

$$QIV_2 = Dem_2 \quad \forall l = 2 \quad (29)$$

$$QRV_3 = Dem_3 \quad \forall l = 3 \quad (30)$$

$$QCV_4 = Dem_4 \quad \forall l = 4 \quad (31)$$

$$ECV = \sum_i \sum_k \sum_m h^* r^* Dist1_{i k m} * W_{i k m} + \sum_j \sum_l \sum_n h^* r^* Dist2_{j l n} * Z_{j l n} + \sum_k \sum_l \sum_p h^* r^* Dist3_{k l p} * B_{k l p} \quad (32)$$

$$ECI = \sum_{l=2} 1.4 * QI_2 \quad (33)$$

$$ECO2 = ECV + ECI \quad (34)$$

$$\begin{aligned} Vol1_{i k m} \in R^+ \quad Vol2_{j l n} \in R^+ \quad Qdc_k \in R^+ \\ Q1_{k l p} \in R^+ \quad Q2_{k l p} \in R^+ \quad Q3_{k l p} \in R^+ \quad Q4_{k l p} \in R^+ \\ QL_{k l p} \in R^+ \quad QI_{k l p} \in R^+ \quad QR_{k l p} \in R^+ \quad QC_{k l p} \in R^+ \\ QLV_{k l p} \in R^+ \quad QIV_{k l p} \in R^+ \quad QRV_{k l p} \in R^+ \quad QCV_{k l p} \in R^+ \\ QLS_{k l p} \in R^+ \quad QIS_{k l p} \in R^+ \quad QRS_{k l p} \in R^+ \quad QCS_{k l p} \in R^+ \\ ECI \in R^+ \quad ECV \in R^+ \quad ECO2 \in R \\ X_k \in \{0, 1\} \quad W_{i k m} \in \{0, 1\} \quad Z_{j l n} \in \{0, 1\} \quad B_{k l p} \in \{0, 1\} \end{aligned} \quad (35)$$

Constraints (2), (3), and (4) distribute the quantities of waste from the collection points (retailers) onto volumes transported to the collection centers of the network. Constraints (5) and (6) require that the volumes of waste transported from the collection points to the collection centers adhere to the minimum and maximum capacities of these centers. Constraint (7) calculates the total quantity of waste delivered to each collection center. Constraints (8), (9), (10), and (11) calculate the quantities of the four different types of waste delivered to each treatment center. Constraints (12), (13), and (14) allocate the quantities of waste from universities onto volumes transported to the treatment centers.

Constraints (15), (16), (17), (18), (19), and (20) calculate the total quantities of type 1, 2, and 3 waste respectively transported from the collection centers of the network to the first, second, and third treatment centers. Constraints (21), (22), and (23) calculate the total quantity of type 4 waste transported to the fourth treatment center from the collection centers and universities. Constraints (24), (25), (26), and (27) ensure the conservation of flows of produced, sold, and stored quantities for each type of waste at each treatment unit. Constraints (28), (29), (30), and (31) ensure the satisfaction of demands for each type of product at each treatment center.

Constraint (32) calculates the CO2 emissions of the transport network. Constraint (33) calculates the CO2 emissions from waste incineration at the second treatment center. Constraint (34) calculate the total CO2 emissions in the studied network, and finally (35) indicates the nature of the decision variables, whether they are binary or real.

5 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The experimental study of the proposed model was implemented in a two-stage multi-level waste collection network. The first stage is made up of a set of retailers (i=6) divided into two groups. The first group is assigned to a sorting zone made up of three sorting centers, while the second group is connected where the waste collected is organic and assigned directly to processing and composting units. The second stage starts at the requested sorting center, where it is sorted according to the nature of the product, before being forwarded to the appropriate processing centers. The center is equipped with four processing centers: a waste storage center, a recycling center, an incinerator and a composting center. Merchandise is transported between the different levels using several vehicles, with a unit cost based on the quantity transported and a maximum loading capacity. The data for the experiment are shown in the following tables.

Table 1: the waste quantities at the collect points and the universities.

	Collect points				Universities	
	1	2	3	4	1	2
Waste quantity	6809	6915	6988	6836	6937	3440

Table 2: the collect center data.

Collect center	Maximum capacity (Kg)	Minimum capacity (Kg)	Operating cost (DA)
1	15,000	9,000	50,000
2	20,000	14,000	80,000
3	9,000	6,000	30,000

Table 3: the distance between the collect points and the collect center

	1st collect point	2nd collect point	3rd collect point
1st collect center	23	51	45
2nd collect center	15	68	48
3rd collect center	40	53	89
4th collect center	47	24	75

Table 4: the distance between collect center and the treatment units

	1st treatment unit	2nd treatment unit	3rd treatment unit	4th treatment unit
1st collect center	14	25	30	65
2nd collect center	28	37	62	44
3rd collect center	39	67	28	23

Table 5: the distance between the universities and the 4th treatment center

	1st treatment unit	2nd treatment unit	3rd treatment unit	4th treatment unit
1st universit	/	/	/	150

Table 9 shows that from the quantities sorted, a transfer is made to the appropriate processing

y				
2 nd universit	/	/	/	160
y				

Table 6: the demands of the treatment units

Treatment unit	1	2	3	4
Demand	6,500	9,800	6,200	14,500

Table 7: the data related to vehicles

Vehicles	Utilisation cost	CO2 rate	Consumption rate
1st set of vehicles (m)	3		
2nd set of vehicles (n)	4	0.34	2.49
3rd set of vehicles (p)	3.5		

5.1 Results

To give a sample of the results obtained, we have implemented the model proposed by the CPLEX12.1 solver. The results obtained are given in Tables 8 and 9. Table 8 represents the quantities that transited from a retailer to a sorting center if the center is operational, for the first stage and Table 9 represents the quantities that transited from a retailer to the composting center in the second stage

Table 8: the waste quantity transported to the collect center from the collect point

Collect center	collect point	The used vehicle	The waste quantity delivered	The total collected quantity
1	1	4	6,633	13,548
	2	3	6,915	
2	1	1	176	14,000
	3	2	6,988	
	4	4	6,836	
3	/	/	/	/

center, which respects the above breakdown and minimizes the transport costs in stage 2

Table 9: the waste quantities repartition at the treatment unit.

Treatment unit	Collect center	The type of waste	The transported quantity from collect center to the treatment unit	The total quantity	The sold quantity	The stored quantity
1	1	1	3251.52	6611.52	6500	111.52
	2		3360			
2	1	2	4877.28	9917.28	9800	117.28
	2		5040			
3	1	3	3116.04	6336.04	6200	136.04
	2		3220			
4	1	4	2303.16	15060.16	14500	560.16
	2		2380			

To provide a clearer understanding of how the centers operate, Figure 2 illustrates the various quantities transformed at each operational center.

Fig2. Quantity delivered from retailers to collection center

The results show that of all the processing centers, only centers 1 and 2 were selected for sorting, while center 3 was put on hold, since the quantities collected during this period did not exceed the capacity of the centers selected by the program, which was designed to minimize the various costs, opening costs and transport costs, while satisfying the processing of the various quantities of waste in full compliance with environmental constraints. The sorted quantities are then returned to the processing centers. The optimal cost for the network studied, which is made up of the transport costs of the system and the cost of

using the treatment center, is estimated at 470,390.88 DA.

This study was accompanied by an evaluation of the CO2 emission rates generated by the means of transport used by the entire network, and by the CO2 emission rates of incineration, which has the highest CO2 weighting in the recycling circuit, as shown in Table 10.

Table 10: the CO2 emission form vehicles

Vehicles	The vehicle	The emitted CO2	The total CO2 emitted from vehicles
1st set of vehicles (m)	1	43.1766	665.43
	2	44.8698	
	3	12.699	
	4	39.7902	
2nd set of vehicles (n)	1	266.679	665.43
	2	0	
	3	0	
	4	0	
3rd set of vehicles (p)	1	0	665.43
	2	258.213	
	3	0	
	4	0	

Estimates of CO2 emissions based on 0.43 DA/Km full load, and a CO2 emission rate of 2.49 Kg CO2/L Harrir and al. (2022) for transport costs and for the incinerator, which emits 1 to 1.4 tonnes

of CO₂ per tonne of waste burned (140%) depending on the reference *Ekonomika. Ž* (2019).

6 CONCLUSION

In this work, we have proposed a configuration for a recycling network linking collection points, sorting centers and processing centers; the aim is to study both the minimization of transport costs and the operating costs of sorting centers, and the minimization of the CO₂ emissions generated. The proposed model effectively solved the problem by

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optimizing the allocation of means of transport from one floor to another, and was also able to help decision-makers determine when sorting centers should be in operation over the horizon, in order to optimize the processing of different types of waste while respecting the environmental footprint.

Our future work will focus on the use of electric vehicles to transfer goods within the recycling network, while further reducing CO₂ emissions.

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